

////////////////////////////////////

CONCEPTUAL DESIGN OF THE INTERACTIVE COMMUNICATION AND CARE ROBOT FOR THE OLDER GENERATION

Ching Yang / Che-Jung Chang / I-chun Chen / Hong-Wei Huang,

Department of Industrial Design, National Yunlin University of Science and Technology / National Chiao Tung University, Institute of Applied Arts / Department of Industrial Design, National Cheng Kung University / Department of Industrial Design, National Yunlin University of Science and Technology, yangj@yuntech.edu.tw / fujibox@hotmail.com / eachchen@hotmail.com / st42294229@yahoo.com.tw

ABSTRACT

This research conducted the daily schedule interview and living survey to four families with members of older generation who aged from 65 to 80, firstly. Then, a questionnaire survey to 86 old peoples about their daily schedules, health care problems and demand for interaction with family members and AIOS life style scale was executed. The study finds that elderly stay at home. These old people usually feature physical capability deterioration, long-term medicine taking, emphasis on exercises, etc; they feel lonely and like others' company and interactions with their children or relatives. Thus, a scenario was developed to depict the health care and interaction demands for old generations in the future, and various possibility of interactive communication. Based on the scenario and with the adoption of high technologies, we proposed two innovative intelligent caring robot design, "MORI" and "Hi - Bee". The research be served as the reference for developing future intelligent robots for older generations.

Keywords: Older Generations, Health Care, Intelligent Robot

INTRODUCTION

BACKGROUND

Nowadays, faced with declining birthrate and aging society phenomenon and complex family structure gradually becomes simple. Older people living alone or in groups become more and more common.

Modern Family's Children leave their home to study or work after growing up, the problem of "empty-nest" adjustment faced by parents. Become an older generation family; Such families, children are outside living and chance of interaction decreases. Older need Communication modes like message, letter, telephone, SMS and MAIL with their children. Electronics technologies including Internet, cell phone and digital media step over time and space limitations, and help people interact and communicate with others ubiquitously. How should people's most basic family life correspond to the ever-changing high-tech era? How to apply high technology (e.g : RFID, GPS, wireless transmission) into the design of products used for old people's interactions, emotional communications and medical care? These questions motivate our study.

RESEARCH PURPOSES

Aiming at families containing old people aged over 65 to 80, this study conducts case interviews with four families and carries out 86 sampling questionnaires for northern, central and southern areas of Taiwan so as to know old people's family life timetable, home care demands, activity preference, interactive and communicative relationships with children, and AIOS life style scale. Then, it summarizes elements of old people's physiological and psychological demands for home life care and uses scenario-oriented method to simulate health care for old people and interaction demands of household life. Emotion perception, wireless transmission and physiological sensing

technology are combined with mechanical structure technique to generate two creative design proposal-robot “MORI” and “Hi-Bee”, for the purpose of verifying the feasibility of future elderly generation’s demands for interaction and communication as well as providing reference for the design and development of future intelligent robots.

METHODS AND PROCEDURES

Research methods include literature review, case interview, questionnaire survey for creative design proposal. Firstly, literature review is to analyze knowledge and theories relevant to the aged trend, life demands, family life interactions & communications, artificial intelligence, etc. Then, case interviews and questionnaire surveys are conducted among the aged in old generation families of Taiwan, so as to generalize and analyze current situations of life schedule, health care, demands for interactions with family, etc and then draw up design guideline. Next, product design method is introduced with “an interactive frame of human, machine and environment” as the core, thus to develop a proposal of new product design. Finally, scenario-oriented method is adopted to present design results and simulate elderly generation’s family life interaction & communication and interactive context of robot, which is used for taking care old people. Conclusions and suggestions are obtained in accordance with research data analysis and research results generalization.

LITERATURE REVIEW

This section investigates old people’s current trends, physical and mental changes and elements of household product design, as well as summarizes and analyzes knowledge and theories relevant to human-computer interaction, scenarios, intelligent robot, etc.

Aging boomers

“Aging boomers” refers to “aging of population” resulted from low birth rate, a decrease in number of teenagers, high ratio of the aged in advanced countries. If this phenomenon lasts a long time, population structure abrupt and labor shortage will appear. It’s estimated that the ratio of the aged in gross population will be 26% in 2030, and countries

in the world will face serious problem of aging society.

Physical and mental changes of the aged

Adults aged over 50 gradually suffer loss in body organs and functions and thus enter an elderly generation, e.g: “the aged”. For people aged over 60, factors like osteoporosis and degenerative nervous system can cause declines in physiological function such as degeneration of joints of hand and foot, insensitive neurotic reactions and disequilibrium. Correspondingly, perceptual capabilities like eyesight, olfaction and touch also changes, and ability to react gradually weakens (Wen-Hung Chao, 1993) . Developments in robotics are reaching the point where robot caregivers and companions for vulnerable members of society are becoming a real possibility . Elderly people are often lonely and in need of companionship and social contact. Some hold that a robot could be a friend substitute and reassure absent families about the well-being of their elderly relative by monitoring and reporting on their health (The American Psychological Association, 1998).

Elements of designing household products for the aged

Physical and mental functions of the elderly gradually decline, so home environment design for these people should make them feel safe, settled and at ease (Ming-Shih Chen, 2005). Products designed for elderly concern three main ergonomics elements: (1) prevent or slow down the deterioration of physical and mental functions; (2) increase the chance of old people’s participation in activities like job, sociality and education; (3) strengthen the supportive system of care for the aged.

Interactions and communications

Interaction refers to a process of successive activities and responses occurred between two living creatures or machines. Interaction contains not only physical movements but also static mental activities (Bolullo, 2001). Communication is mainly accomplished through language expression or non-verbal communication, e.g. eye contact, gesture, countenance. (Harada, Akira 1996) believes that the key point of communication interface design is not

controlling the “object” but realizing the mutual relationships between human and machine. Moreover, relationship design can be generated through an experience between human and human. This could guide future design of interactions between family members.

Scenario-oriented method

Scenario-oriented method is an important way of clarifying unknown future (Pierre Wack, 1985). In 1992, Anderson proposed two features of scenario design: (1) scenario refers to a description of a series of or procedural activities or events, and a state is converted into another possible state; (2) scenario is to describe the system from the viewpoint of external user rather than from the angle of the system. Through image presentation and scenario description, this study introduces Ubiquitous technology concepts to propose various hypothetical solutions for future interactions & communications between family members.

Intelligent Robot

In a broad sense, intelligent robot refers to robot that is subsequent to second-generation robot and has various kinds of sensors and ability to judge. As technology advances, it’s more proper to explain intelligent robot as robot with a high intelligent capacity, e.g.: “high-function robot” such as Atomic Energy Robot, Universe Robot, Ocean Robot, and Care Robot. Technique essential for developing this kind of Rot is called sophisticated robot technique. At the same time, Robot therapy for elderly has been conducted:

1. Paro, the seal robot, brought elderly about psychological improvements. (Journal of Gerontology: MEDICAL SCIENCES Copyright 2004 by The Gerontological Society of America,2004)
2. AIBO, An entertainment robot ,was an effective rehabilitation tool in the treatment of severely demented patients. (Kazuyoshi Wada and Takanori Shibata, 2007)

CURRENT SITUATIONS INVESTIGATION

CASE INTERVIEW OBJECTS AND INTERVIEW IMPLEMENTATION

From November, 2010 to December, 2010, this study conducts case interviews with Lin’s family of New Taipei City, Ting’s family of Taipei City and Chen’s family of Tainan City. The interview content includes home environment, life schedule, activity preference, physical aging, health care and interaction and communication with family members. Life details are recorded and pictures of activities are taken. Table 1 shows the basic information and interview record abstract of interviewees.

Case 1: Ms. Lin	
Age	80
Residence	Sanchong District, New Taipei City
House	Floor 4 of old apartment
Area	About 105.785 m ²
Age o f building	43 years

Features:

1. Her husband has died and she lives together with her 50-year-old son. Daughter-in-law and grandson live abroad.
2. Get up at 5 a.m. and go to bed at 10 p.m. Live a regular life.
3. Household activities: worship, buy food, cook, watch TV, feed the bird, water the flowers, etc.
4. Physical conditions: osteoarthritis, frequently taking medicine. She is afraid of light and has to wear sunglasses because of eye disease. Amnesia causes forgetting to add seasoning when cooking.
5. Make phone call with children or grandson weekly.

Case 2: Ms. Ding	
Age	84
Residence	Da An district, Taipei City
House	Floor 6 of apartment building
Area	About 122.314 m ²
Age o f building	11 years

Features:

1. Her husband has died. She lives together with 59-year-old son, 57-year-old daughter-in-law and 23-year-old granddaughter.
2. Get up at 6 a.m. and go to bed at 8 p.m. Live a regular life.
3. Household activities: read English, attend class, swim, cook dinner, watch TV, etc.
4. Physical conditions: love learning. Regular swimming and Exercises guarantee healthy body. She can take a bus alone.
5. Contact with family members through cell phone if go out.

	Case 3: Mr. Chen	Case4: Ms. Chen
Age	70	66
Residence	Tainan City	"
House	Three-floor townhouse.	"
Area	About 247.934m ²	"
Age of building	23 years	"

- Features:
1. Mr. Chen has retired and lives together with his 66-year-old wife. He has three sons and a granddaughter, and the eldest child is a doctor who is married.
 2. Mr. Chen and Mrs. Chen get up at 6 a.m. and go to bed at 11 p.m. Live a regular life.
 3. Household activities: they both love listening to the radio, watching TV, visiting relatives and friends, walking and riding.
 4. The husband helps his wife do housework and likes writing diaries as well as talking about politics. The wife needs to cook meals, buy food, do housework, etc.
 5. Physical conditions: they both suffer from hypertension and have to take drug at definite time. Mr. Chen also suffers from heart disease and arthritis; Mrs. Chen, who suffers from osteoporosis, gets tired easily and has to lie frequently.
 6. Have phone call with the youngest son regularly. In holidays, son, daughter-in-law and granddaughter go to reunite with them. This family is quite harmonious and happy.

Table 1 Basic information of case interview

CASE ANALYSIS AND GENERALIZATION

According to the case of health, home activities and the needs of the robot, can be summarized as following points, thus to provide reference for future design development.

1. Robots can assisted analyze interactive functions of voice and images.
 - As elderly often forget to Measures the blood pressure or take medicine, so regular voice reminds is added on robot.
 - Elderly often yearn to preclude worries, so the robot will be designed with the function of remember past things, enabling the elderly feel aftertaste at any time.
 - As elderly have needs of learning languages or talents, so the robot will not only join the

teaching function and interactive features, but set the screen touching importation and recognition.

- Elderly are accustomed to telephone their family in order to sustain natural affection.
- and they can deliver the image and dialogue each other with robot's screen and its system of dialogue .

2. Robots assisted analyze movements of the elderly body.

- Elderly live alone and develop action inconvenience, health problems such as care and security etc, the robot can be imported video surveillance and alarm system device and notify family or medical system in emergency.
- Elderly 's hearing, vision, physical fitness gradually decline, the robot can be given voice identification or image recognition functions and help takes the thing also act at any time to take care of the nearest.
- For the elderly degenerative arthritis, gout, bone spurs and other ailments, the robot can help to complete housework or assist in medication so that patients can reduce pain and comfortable nurse their mind and body.

CONTENT AND IMPLEMENTATION OF QUESTIONNAIRE SURVEY

From January 2011 to February 2011, this study aimed at Taiwan over 50 year-old elders in middle and older generation family.

The subjects of this study are families with middle and old aged people over 50 in Taiwan. Sampling investigation is implemented according to geographic areas: northern, middle and southern districts. A total of 150 questionnaires are mailed to participants' parents and relatives, and 86 questionnaires are recycled representing a response rate of 57.3%.

QUESTIONNAIRE TESTEES'S BASIC INFORMATION

According to survey results, Female participants account for 58.1% of all testees and the male make up 39.5%. With regard to testee's age, 51-55 and 56-60 years account for 29.1% and 25.6% respectively. Couples' ages are mainly 51-55, which makes up

29.1%. In terms of educational background, college degree and senior high school/vocational high school accounts for 37.2% and 36% respectively. Government employees & teachers and housewives respectively make up 29.1% and 20.9% of all occupational types. In terms of retirement, people not retired yet account for 45.3% and the retired account for 40.7%. Monthly pension and regular salary make up 23.3% and 19.7% of family income resources respectively. Family income amount mainly falls between 30 and 50 thousand NTDs, which account for 23.3%. The ratio of testee's living along with family members is 86%. Among inmates, the percentage of couple is the highest-75%, and the next is son with ratios of 56.9% and 32.5%. 66.3% of the testees reside in Taichung. Town house is the main house style and makes up 46%. Most of the habitable areas (i.e. 37.2%) are 69.421 to 99.174 m². Residence period focuses on 21to30 years, which account for 23.3%.

LIFE TIMETABLE AND PREFERRED ACTIVITIES OF TESTEES

Table 2 summarizes and shows questionnaire survey results and statistical results of items 15-17. The top three indoor activities favored by testees are watching TV (86%), reading books & newspapers (55.8%) and cooking (38.4%). The top three most popular outdoor activities are walking in park (55.8%), visiting relatives & friends (34.8%) and shopping (32.5%). Top three acquirements of personal interest are learning about computer (23.2%), song party (20.9%) and going to exhibition (18.6%)

INTERACTIVE AND COMMUNICATIVE ACTIVITIES OF OLD PEOPLE'S HOUSEHOLD LIFE

According to results of items 18 to 20 shown in Table 3, the top three family gathering activities most popular with testees are chatting (68.6%), watching TV (63.9) and dinning together at home (60.4). With regard to activities conducted when family members back home, room cleaning accounts for the highest ratio (33.7%), and then is purchasing food & daily necessities (29%). The top three ways of contact with families are cell phone (83.7%), phone (66.2%) and SMS (63.2%).

15. Popular indoor activities*	Watching TV	74	86.0
	Reading book & newspaper	48	55.8
	Cooking	33	38.3
	Cleaning	32	37.2
	Listening to music	28	32.5
	On the Internet	26	30.2
	Tea drinking and chatting	24	27.9
	Worship	20	23.2
	Listening to the radio	17	19.7
	Karaoke	16	18.6
	Caring for grandchild	12	13.9
	Taking care of pets	6	6.9
	Playing Mahjong	5	5.8
Others	3	3.4	
16. Favorite outdoor activities*	Walking in garden	48	55.8
	Visiting relatives & friends	30	34.8
	Shopping	28	32.5
	Temple fairs	27	31.3
	Volunteer's activity	26	30.2
	Go mountain climbing	16	18.0
	Chatting	15	17.4
	Others	12	13.9
	Swimming	10	11.6
	Husbandry	9	10.4
	Bike riding	8	9.3
	Going to cinema	6	6.9
	Playing badminton	4	4.6
Taking a walk with dog or bird	4	4.6	
Playing croquet	0	0.0	
17. Personal interests & specialties*	Learning about computer	20	23.2
	Song party	18	20.9
	Going to exhibition	16	18.6
	Learning ikebana and gardening	15	17.4
	Chi Kung & Tai-Chi	15	17.4
	Class of scripture reading	11	12.7
	Learning at community college	10	11.6
	Learning handicraft	9	10.4
	Going to library	9	10.4
	Folk dance club	7	8.1
Garden club	7	8.1	
Learning English and Japanese	4	4.6	
Playing chess	3	3.4	
Total	86	100.0	

Table 2 Statistics of old people's household activities and hobbies
(* Multiple choices)

Item	Content	Frequenc y	Percenta ge
------	---------	---------------	----------------

Item	Content	Frequency	Percentage
18. Family gathering activities*	Chatting	59	68.6
	Watching TV	55	63.9
	Dining together	52	60.4
	Travelling	35	40.6
	Eating out	30	34.8
	Visiting relatives & friends	21	24.4
	Shopping	20	23.2
	Having fun with grandchild	20	23.2
	Worship at temple	15	17.4
	Karaoke	15	17.4
	Walking in park	14	16.2
	Going to cinema	7	8.1
	Mahjong	6	6.9
	Playing Mahjong	6	6.9
19. Activities when family members back home*	Room cleaning	29	33.7
	Purchasing food	25	29.0
	Purchasing daily necessities	25	29.0
	Cook meals	24	27.9
	Washing clothes	20	23.2
	Offering living costs	19	22.0
	Accompanying the aged to hospital	16	18.6
	Device repair	15	17.4
	Dealing with bill	13	15.1
	Taking blood pressure & blood sugar	12	13.9
	Others	12	13.9
	Massage	10	11.6
	Sorting the memo	4	4.6
	Cutting nail or hair	4	4.6
Separating drug boxes	4	4.6	
20. Ways of contact with family members*	Cell phone call	72	83.7
	Phone call	57	66.2
	SMS	20	23.2
	Skype or MSN	13	15.1
	E-mail	11	12.7
	Others	5	5.8
	Facebook	3	3.4
Writing letter	0	0.0	
Total		86	100.0

Table 3 Statistics of old people's interactions & communications in household life (* Multiple choices)

LIFE STYLE FACTOR ANALYSIS AND DENOMINATION

Factors with feature number over 1 are extracted to obtain 10 factors. However, factor scree plot shows that factor quantities of items 5 to 6 tend to be stable, with cumulative variance of 6 factors greatest. Therefore, 6 factors are used for factor analysis.

Statistical software spss is used for factor analysis of old people's life style, and six kinds of factors are denominated as follows:

No	Content	F 1	F 2	F 3	F 4	F 5	F 6
25	travelling abroad yearly	.731	.029	-.021	.124	.098	-.070
22	regular exercises	.686	.126	-.153	.005	-.188	.014
11	informing family members of tracks when going out	.588	-.353	-.141	.079	.130	.148
16	picking grandchild up	.560	-.181	.157	.198	-.002	.042
19	fond of novel products	.460	.094	.109	-.065	.244	-.055
02	watching shopping ad. frequently	.374	.232	.269	-.346	.304	-.293
21	ikebana & raising pet	.352	.059	-.040	.271	.065	.231
12	active in sociality	.073	.750	.017	-.132	.137	.069
10	eat and drink well; both meat and vegetables okay	-.052	.672	.164	.061	-.162	-.305
04	budgeting carefully	.321	-.537	.212	.064	.032	-.393
15	fond of politics program	.144	.422	.196	.227	.385	.144
20	afraid of being alone	.000	-.278	.687	-.137	-.073	.316
14	like dropping around and chatting	-.013	.217	.684	.112	.009	-.069
23	hypomnesia	.042	.078	.666	-.154	.118	.034
01	cleaning	.103	.014	-.053	.639	-.119	.029
18	dislike long journey	-.109	.281	.336	-.602	.078	.227
06	satisfied with current situation	.163	-.063	-.052	.562	-.410	.188
09	participation in party hold by relatives or friends	.382	.360	.066	.558	.276	-.028
24	like quietness	.319	.068	-.061	-.427	-.390	.326
05	Buying lotto ticket	.101	.017	-.010	-.084	.706	-.025
03	frequently watching regular TV program	.037	.028	.043	-.094	.566	.066
17	concerned about current affairs	.306	-.207	-.274	.071	.359	.016
08	the children seldom get back home	.065	.035	.088	-.103	-.044	.509
13	expecting conversations with children	-.162	-.202	.284	.224	.154	.507
07	light diet	.097	.039	-.444	.240	.062	.497
Feature value		2.718	2.155	2.138	2.111	1.825	1.513
Explained variance %		10.87	8.622	8.552	8.442	7.301	6.053
Cumulative variance %		10.87	19.49	28.04	36.48	43.78	49.84
		2	4	5	8	8	1
Factor denomination		Lear ning- zealo us	Passi onat e	Livel y and conv ersab le	Cont ente d and happ y	Publi c affair s enth usias tic	Lonel y and econ omic al

Table 4 Factor analysis of old people's life style

- **The learning-zealous:** Refers to old people who pursue life quality, like learning new knowledge, and carefully think about their life planning.
- **The passionate:** The table shows that some elderly don't stick at trifles and are always quite enthusiastic about politics and life.
- **The lively and conversable:** Results generalized in the table show that some old people dislike being alone and often chat with others as well as drop around. They are often forgetful and need other's help and reminding.
- **Contented and happy:** Some of the aged like travelling with others, and are quite optimistic and fond of liveliness.
- **The public-affairs-enthusiastic:** Older people enthusiastic about public affairs always pay attention to all social events and regularly watch certain TV programs.
- **The lonely and economical:** As children go out to work or study, the elderly often feel lonely. Worried about child's daily life, they are quite economical in the hope of assisting their children.

A DISCUSSION AND ANALYSIS OF QUESTIONNAIRE RESULTS

Through questionnaire survey and factor analysis, this study summarizes six life style factors of the aged: "learning-zealous", "passionate", "lively and conversable", "contented and happy", "public-affairs-enthusiastic", "lonely and economical". These factors show empty-nest-stage old people's demands on life, e.g. relative or friend's accompanying, assistance in daily life, schedule reminding and information receiving. These summarized results are necessary bases for this study.

CREATIVE PROPOSAL-ROBOT DESIGN

PROPOSAL 1: HI-BEE

This Concept is produce by the factor of "The learning-zealous" and "The lively and conversable".

Design conditions and concepts of Hi-Bee

This study proposes a design guideline that is centered on old people's daily reactive behaviors and processes and applies the most natural

communication mode between human into the design. The aged gradually decline in physiology and psychology, so single function of accompanying is not enough. Multiple function demands are needed to assist the elderly in daily life, such as cleaning house, getting distant objects and welcoming visitors. The robot can implement simple missions exclusive of complex tasks like cooking. The operation is controlled by voice and the user just need to command an instruction to the robot. The shape of the robot is developed from industrious bee. As living space narrows, the jump ability and convenience increase. The wing for flying can reduce space occupied by the robot; round shape create light and nimble sense of bees; high technologies are introduced into the design, which is based on future elderly generation's household life and develops a family interaction & communication platform effectively integrating human, machine and environment.

Mechanical principle of Hi-Bee

"Hi-Bee"(Figure 1) possesses various functions such as interactive information, leaving message, recording events, memo reminding, voice-control speaking, voice and text recognition, as well as carrying and taking objects. Technologies and function applications of each part of Hi-Bee are explained as below:

- (1) Signal light: the hollowed area is for receiving outside information. The twinkle of red light means receiving information.

Figure 1 structure diagram of mechanical principle of robot "Hi-Bee"

- (2) Interactive Interface: it is a combination of interface display with multimedia device, and has functions of audio-visual play, voice-control conversation, message, real-time interaction, monitoring, entertainment, etc.
- (3) LED Display: changes in color represent different situations. For example, blue means flying, red means charging, red and blink means alarm of danger, yellow refers to showing multimedia.
- (4) Charge base : plays a role of control center to supply electricity. The use of network transmission device acts as high-speed computation mechanism.
- (5) Mechanical legs : skid-proof material at the end benefits grabbing.
- (6) Rotating joint: control the flight directions.
- (7) Flight Wing: the technology of turboprop is hidden beneath the wing to help with rotating shaft raising and landing, hanging, direction rotation, etc.

the storeroom, Mum shouts Hi-Bee who is upstairs, hoping that it can go downstairs to help her. Hi-Bee hears Mum's shout, and then promptly fly downstairs and freely flies in the narrow room (Figure2-d).

Figure 2-a

Figure 2-b

Figure 2-c

Figure 2-d

Use contexts of Hi-Bee

"Hi-Bee", an integration of high technologies, has interactive communication functions of interactive information, leaving message, recording events, memo-reminding, voice-control speaking, voice & text recognition, helping human carry objects, etc. With round shape and strong futuristic feel, it will be a new family member of future home care. In the following, scenario-oriented method will be used to simulate future life and communication mode by virtue of "Hi-Bee".

Scene 1: Interactive context design of life care: once the father or the child gets home from work or school, Hi-Bee will promptly fly to the door and greet them, and ask if everything goes well. (Figure 2-a)

Scene 2: Interactive context design of multimedia presentation : the grandma, with physical disability, is not able to move freely and get the radio. Utilizing the inbuilt projection function of Hi-Bee can play CD (Figure 2-b).

Scene 3: Interactive context design of searching and getting objects : grandpa suffers from diabetes and has to take medicine, but he often forget to do this. Hi-Bee can get the drug for grandpa and grandpa can take medicine at certain time without walking with a stick to get the drug (Figure 2-c).

Scene 4: Interactive context design of mobility : in

DESIGN PROPOSAL 2- MORI CARE

This Concept is produce by the factor of "The passionate" and "The lonely and economical".

Design conditions and conceptions of Mori Care

The design of Mori Care(Figure 3) aims at current elderly generation. As children work outside, common demands of empty-nest period appear, such as child's phone call, family member's care and self care in daily life. Context and functions are set according to future demands on daily life and communication. Physical care includes medical reminders such as medicine taking, seeing a doctor and rehabilitation. Mental care, psychological support for the elderly included, is for relieving the mood and significantly improving the society's ignorance of the aged generation. With regard to appearance design, the light and agile shape endows MORI with an appearance and communication interface that is human-like, vivid and lovely, and emphasizes interaction with the aged so as to make old people's home life full of joy. The design of neck and wheel makes MORI can conduct plenty of vivid body movements, thus to bring the elderly new communication experience and funny interactive mode.

Figure 3 structure diagram of mechanical principle of robot "Mori Care"

Well-developed high-tech elements are also integrated, such as feel perception, wireless transmission, environmental perception system, image projection, etc. During interaction, kind and interesting facial expressions and actions, information presentation, touch and petting are used to express different moods and interactions between family members, so as to provide considerate human-centered services for the aged.

Mechanical principle of Mori Care

- (1) Touch Sensor: establish emotional relationship with robot through touch. Changes in LED information show the robot's self mood and perceptions of environment.
- (2) Microphone: visitors' voices are recorded to judge their identities in terms of voice.
- (3) Projector: set on the nose to project information image onto the plane, such as family member's phone and health report.
- (4) Momentum Wheel Motor: differential drive is used for direction turning, rotating and body swaying as well as diversified vivid and interesting movements.
- (5) Ultrasonic Obstacle Sensor: set at the lower end, so as to detect obstacle and thus move in the space freely and safely.
- (6) Touch Screen: functions of leaving message, real-time interaction, monitoring, entertainment, etc., such as security & management system, 3C household electrical appliance and management, weather, time service, audio-visual record and MSN information receiving.
- (7) Speaker: voice-control conversation, which can relieve family member's mood at proper time.
- (8) Camera: memorize visitors' images.

Figure 4-a

Figure4-b

Figure 4-c

Figure4-d

Use context of Mori Care

This contextual design adopts scenario-oriented method to simulate life and communication mode of older generation who use "MORI Care":

Scene 1: call video projection : when grandpa sits in the rocking chair, Mori helps him answer his granddaughter's phone, projects the girl's image on the wall and makes her talk with grandpa (Figure 4-a).

Scene 2: home security monitoring : One day, when grandma is boiling water, a courier comes to deliver parcel. After receiving the parcel, grandma forgets the boiling water and begins to have a phone call with another old lady. Mori reminds grandma is boiling water, She have to close it.(Figure 4-b)

Scene 3: emergency notice : one day afternoon, grandpa is at home alone, feel dizzy and unable to stand up. Grandpa told Mori to call grandma back and give assistance (Figure 4-c).

Scene 4: daily medical reminding : When grandma comes home after buying fish, Mori gets besides grandma: "grandma, have you bought fish? You come back home late, remember to take medicine after breakfast! And in the afternoon, don't forget to ask grandpa to fetch drug at the pharmacy!" (Figure 4-d)

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Through analyzing three family cases as well as questionnaire investigations into the life timetable, interactions and communications of 86 older people, and proposing relevant conceptual design of robot used for caring this population, this study presents following conclusions and suggestions:

- Environment observations and literature researches show that human behavior is not constrained to language communication and eye contact, gesture, expression and behavior play a more important role in home life. Kansei design can be applied into household environment and objects. Therefore, the design for old people's interaction and communication should make human and material combined more closely so as to achieve emotional connection.
- Contextual design is used to simulate the use context of future interactive communication device, so as to know demands for interactive communication of household life, such as care for the aged, home security, associations of different life schedules and spaces, etc.
- In current older generation family, face-to-face communications decrease because children are busy with work and their timetables are different. Moreover, house configuration results in diversified demands on communication. It's necessary to develop a kind of interaction and communication platform that has functions of message leaving, multimedia, voice recognition, sound-control speaking, security monitoring, household electrical appliances operating, and information transmitting. This is a reference for commercialization of high-tech industries and a definite trend of consumer market.
- Future family interaction and communication device will possess various kinds of functions including game, leisure and entertainment, thus to bring more convenient communication mode for future family life and make technological products more human-oriented. This kind of device can not only provide considerate and faithful support, service and communication, but also generate substantial human-centered efficacy and can be considered as a family member by virtue of an interactive platform that integrates multiple functions with high technology.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

This research was supported by National Science Council Integrated Program's "The Study on Ambient Environment in Daily Activity and Design its Interactive Communicative System" (2/2)(NSC 99-

2220-E-224-009-). Special thanks to Tzu- Hsiang, Chou in the questionnaire statistics.

REFERENCES

- Wen-hung Chao.(1993).The 37 old aged case researches of decision process of living arrangement and house space problems in Taichung, Institute of Architecture, Tunghai University, Master's Thesis
- Ming-Shih Chen & Chia-Ching Wu.(2005). The Research of The Microwave Oven Interface Operating from The Viewpoint of Aged User, Department of Industrial Design, Tunghai University.
- Roberto Bolullo.(2001). "Interaction design: More than interface", available at <http://bolullo.com/roberto/topics.htm> 4. Anderaon, J.S, and Durney, B, 1992, "Using scenarios in deficiency-driven requirements engineering" In proceedings of the IEEE International Symposium on Requirements Engineering. Washington, pp.134-141
- Y Tian-Z.(1996). translated by Chong-bin H, Reactive Interface Design—And the external world as the next generation user interface response relationship, 1996 Sino-Japanese Design Education Symposium, National Yunlin University, Department of Industrial Design, Taiwan, pp.8-15.
- Pierre Wack.(1985). Scenarios: uncharted waters ahead. Harvard Business Review,63(5).pp.73-89.
- Hong-I H.(2008).A Study Of The Generic Family Living Style And The Communication Pattern Among Family Members, Department of Design, National Yunlin University of Science and Technology, Taiwan, pp.14-18.
- Toshiyo Tamura,Satomi Yonemitsu,Akiko Itoh,Daisuke Oikawa,Akiko Kawakami,Yuji Higashi,Toshiro Fujimooto,and Kazuki Nakajima. (2004).Is an Entertainment Robot Useful in the Care of Elderly People With Severe Dementia?Department of Gerontechnology, National Institute for Longevity Sciences, Aichi, Japan.Fujimoto Hayasuzu Hospital, Miyazaki, Japan.Green Home for the Geriatric Facility, Miyazaki, Japan.
- Amanda Sharkey and Noel Sharkey.(2011). Children, the Elderly, and Interactive Robots Anthropomorphism and Deception in Robot Care and Companionship, IEEE ROBOTICS & AUTOMATION MAGAZINE.
- The American Psychological Association.(1998).Older Adults' Health and Age-Related Changes: Reality Versus Myth
- Kazuyoshi Wada and Takanori Shibata, Member, IEEE.(2007).Living With Seal Robots—Its Sociopsychological and Physiological Influences on the Elderly at a Care House. IEEE TRANSACTIONS ON ROBOTICS, VOL. 23, NO. 5.